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EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING LINGUISTICS TERMS TO PHILOLOGICAL STUDENTS

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Abstract. The article describes the role of students' terminological dictionary in the development of terminological competence of philology students, the scientific-methodical basis and aspects of its organization, and its importance.

Key words: *term, terminology, terminological competence, terminological dictionary, student's terminological dictionary, terminographic explanation.*

Today, the service of pedagogical higher education institutions is great in the training of pedagogic personnel. Therefore, in pedagogical institutions of higher education, we developed recommendations on improving the training sessions of the Uzbek language and literature course, providing them with educational literature at the level of the current requirements, and in addition, on the effective organization of the training sessions. output is important.

In general, the pedagogical possibilities of improving the quality of teaching language and literature in the educational system, in particular, enriching the Uzbek language and Uzbek literature course with practical content and improving the methodological foundations in accordance with the modern development trends of these subjects plays an important role.

Sh. Yusupova says that using the "Interpreting method" in mother tongue lessons is effective:

1. Interpretation helps to understand the theoretical information about the mother tongue.
2. Interpretation refers to the application of theoretical information in practice.
3. It helps to develop oral speech.
4. Coordinates relations of orthographic and orthographic norms.
5. Theoretical information is emphasized to the students during the entire lesson" [1].

The theoretical information learned by the student in the "interpretation method", scientific terms are widely used in practice, it prepares the ground for the development of oral and written speech in students, and the application of the knowledge gained in their specialty in their work. As a result of interpretation of theoretical information in Uzbek language classes, it serves to

develop students' terminological competence and put into practice the knowledge they have learned during the lesson.

Non-traditional methods of education in order to focus students' attention, to learn something from the lesson, to think creatively, in lectures and practical classes of linguistics, in general, every topic studied in linguistics classes need to be used effectively. One such method is educational games. "Games and tasks organized in the mother tongue, depending on the purpose:

- 1) Games aimed at mastering linguistic knowledge;
- 2) We divided students into two types, such as games aimed at increasing vocabulary and developing speech.

Games aimed at mastering the rules, concepts and definitions of the native language are part of linguistic games. The main part of the main games-tasks organized in the mother tongue are games aimed at increasing the vocabulary of students and developing their speech"[2].

It is appropriate to use educational games, taking into account the age characteristics of students, the level of independent work, the level of knowledge, their activity, resourcefulness, initiative, knowledge, and inquisitiveness. When choosing educational games, it is important to take into account the learning opportunities of each group of students, the purpose of the language and literature topics being studied.

At a time when science and technology are rapidly developing, and people feel a great need to work with various sources, educational and terminological dictionaries, encyclopedic dictionaries, acquiring the skills and qualifications to find terms in dictionaries is today's linguistic education. is one of the important tasks facing the country. The educational game used for this purpose gives good results. The game can be used in the reinforcement part of the lesson. In this case, it is necessary to have a spelling dictionary and terminological dictionaries in the hands of students. It is necessary to quickly find the terms related to the topic and science with the help of dictionaries, to understand the information related to the meaning and application of the terms. Using the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language [3], the explanatory dictionary of linguistic terms [4] and other dictionaries related to linguistics gives effective results.

It is necessary for the teacher to teach students effective ways of working with dictionaries. Because textbooks and dictionaries are the basis and necessary tools of linguistics education. One of the main factors of developing students' creative outlook and speech is working on dictionaries. Dictionaries are a rich resource that serves to increase the level of creative thinking, oral and written

thinking of students. It is difficult to imagine linguistics training without dictionaries. It is desirable to include them in the main literature, to use dictionaries effectively in the course of training. Dictionaries are a source of knowledge and a teaching tool. Interpreting the meaning of a term or words, learning how to use a certain word, correcting errors, studying the explanation, alternatives, origin of the term, choosing synonyms, synonyms, and adverbs. creative-practical tasks can be done with the help of dictionaries. If dictionaries are treated as the first useful assistant, if they are used effectively in the course of training, the level of knowledge of the lessons and students will increase even more. First of all, it is necessary to pay attention to their vocabulary in linguistics and literature classes in order to strengthen students' knowledge of science, independent thinking, and mastery of specialized terms. Students' terminological vocabulary is improved through the scientific literature, textbooks, collected materials. Collecting terms, using them correctly in speech and professional processes, pronouncing them, writing without mistakes, improving spelling literacy in the student creates terminological competence.

One of the cases observed in the field of linguistics and literature is that the student is not able to distinguish many terms in the field of the subjects he is studying and does not know the meaning of the terms. It is appropriate for the teacher to start working with the dictionary in the course of training, first of all, by creating a dictionary for the student. If there is an explained word or phrase in the course of lessons and training, in textbooks and manuals, it becomes a habit to include it in the dictionary on a regular basis, if the student does not stop this tradition until he completes higher education. , gives an efficient result. First of all, each student should create a set of terminological dictionaries in the form of a methodical guide for himself, using the terminological dictionaries attached to the textbooks and exercises. If necessary terms are written down in the "Dictionary Notebook" prepared by the students during the lessons, it will serve as the main material in the performance of tasks and assignments and in the future work activities. Inter-group, inter-course, inter-faculty competitions organized in order to increase the terms in the terminological dictionary increase students' love for science and their specialty, teach them to work independently, use libraries and scientific literature, read books, learn strengthens the need for.

Terminological dictionary is a special dictionary necessary for each field. A terminological or special dictionary is a type of encyclopedic dictionary that covers any specialized terms - the names of concepts and objects in a particular

field of knowledge and scientific and technical branches, explains and interprets them [5]. So, the terminological dictionary covers the terms of one field. A terminological dictionary can be monolingual or bilingual, trilingual or multilingual.

In the development of terminological competence of philological students in specialized subjects, teaching them to work with terminological dictionaries and maintain such a special dictionary has an important scientific-theoretical, practical and methodical essence.

For this purpose, the following recommendations and tips are given regarding the maintenance of the "Student's Terminological Dictionary" in the first lessons of specialized subjects:

1. To maintain such a dictionary, if the student first has a personal computer, a special folder called "My Terminological Dictionary" is opened or a notebook is kept. Files are opened in alphabetical order within the folder. If the dictionary is in the form of a notebook, it is divided into pages in alphabetical order.
2. The dictionary is regularly maintained in alphabetical order based on current writing.
3. The term explained in the terminological notes in the dictionary is taken as a title and is written in bold letters.
4. In the dictionary, the terms of linguistics and literary studies can be noted separately, and in turn, they can be divided into fields and departments. For example, the terms of the science of linguistics are related to phonetics and phonology, terms related to the field of lexicology, terms related to the theory of linguistics; terms of the science of literature as terms related to literary types and genres, as well as terms related to the language of artistic works.
5. During or at the end of each lecture, in the process of preparation for practical and seminar sessions, terms related to the topic and their historical and etymological source, explanation, meaning, if any, variants, synonyms, Uzbek alternatives, if necessary, examples and proofs are recorded.

Therefore, it is necessary to work with dictionaries as a component of linguistic training. If the student does not have a terminological dictionary, we should teach and interest them to create a terminological dictionary and use it. Ensuring a thorough mastery of linguistics begins with understanding its terms.

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